

MEASURING THE COMPANY'S PERFORMANCE TO AVOID TURMOIL - AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

The financial crisis of 2008 - so far has been followed by a long global recession. There has been and continues to be a period of volatility and economic uncertainty that we are experiencing today and that will accompany us for a long time to come. Firms need to analyze their strategies, find the best way to create value for the consumer, and constantly look for sustainable profitability sources.

Keywords: *performance, strategies, firm, recessions, crisis, uncertainty, performance, turbulence*

Introduction. This article influences the business environment. I believe it will not come as a surprise if I say that in times of economic recession, people buy less and companies choose whether to invest or not depending on consumer behaviour. There is an interdependent and complex relation between recession and investment - the longer the recession lasts, the more the investment tends to lag behind the resumption of consumption by the consumers. There is a risk that investments will become counter - cyclical, i.e. slow down instead of supporting economic recovery. When recessions are less frequent or shorter, firms invest more and tend to divide their investments more evenly between different components of the business. Most of the time, the influences between the company and the macro-social environment are reciprocal. Any country that invests in education and culture will be able to influence many people to read and buy books. In turn, people who read will perpetuate the behaviour as other people imitate them. These trends will diversify the book market. It is extremely important that companies pay close attention to external factors that may influence the business and incorporate these influences into their strategic decisions. The monitoring of external influences becomes essential in conditions of uncertainty and economic turmoil.

Theoretical analysis. Trying to restructure a company in the midst of a crisis is not the right time, it is a risky time. During the crisis, the stabilization of the system takes place and reconstruction can begin only after the crisis ended. Quiet periods are not a good time for restructuring; companies only question their business model when they get into trouble. Current economic performance is not an effective predictor of the future. From a strategic point of view, the company is healthy if it can meet the potential challenges of the future, not if it is successful now. Firms evaluate in a particular context, composed of specific forces with variable impact. We can identify certain typical indicators that can predict the strategic health of the company and that require close monitoring. These indicators are:

- Changing the wishes and needs of the customers.
- Decreased raw material resources.
- The emergence of technological innovations capable of changing the market and the nature of the business;
- Strong tendency to concentrate suppliers of products or services, through organic growth and / or acquisitions by other companies;

- Changing the lifestyle and work attitude of employees;
- Increasing long-term demographic processes, such as increasing the share of the elderly population in the total population.

We need to look closely at the evolution of the company's main profitability indicators, such as sales, revenue, number of customers, customer preferences, market share, rate of recommendation of our products by customers. If we have relatively uniform historical data, a good technique is forecasting based on time series. If there are large discrepancies between the values of the series or we anticipate changes in the trend, the time series do not provide satisfactory information about the future of the company. Crises usually disrupt data and reduce the accuracy of time series forecasts. In times of uncertainty, many companies prefer to use judgment-based forecasting techniques. Expert juries and the Delphi method are the most common. Both methods are based on the selection of top specialists in the field. Specialists are asked to make predictions about future developments in various areas related to the company's prospects and to justify these forecasts. Synthesis of predictions by third parties is developed and successive rounds of forecasting are organized until a consensus is reached.

The essential condition for maintaining the strategic health of the company is the continuous monitoring of the market, for the early detection of signals that may affect the future of the company. The firm must accurately estimate the cost of underestimating or overestimating the forecast. In normal times, when sales are relatively stable and market movements are small, the forecast has a low standard deviation and the cost of underestimation or overestimation may be low. However, in the face of turbulence and economic uncertainty, the standard deviation is rising, and the cost of the erroneous forecast could be devastating for the business. For example, firms that rely on a larger market in the future and produce in excess may suffer large losses if the forecast does not come true. In general, in uncertain times, conservative forecasts have a lower cost than optimistic ones, because losses from unmet demand are lower than losses from unsold production and inventories. There are four remedies for the scenario in which the strategic health of the company is threatened. These are:

- Disruptive innovation
- Strengthening the company's leadership
- Experimenting on a limited scale with new solutions to test how the market reacts
- Selling the business

Disruptive innovation is the safest, but also the most difficult. It involves the institutionalization of the innovative effort within the organization. The business model is the most important barrier that prevents companies from innovating. Every company has a business model, and the company can invest in developments that help it make money, if it takes into account the way its business model is structured. If an innovation does not allow the company to make more money in the way the company is organized to earn it, then the company will not be able to implement the innovation. It is not about minor innovations, but about revolutionary or disruptive innovations. To find these innovations and to translate them into reality, the company must design a completely different business model from the existing one, i.e. change the way it was designed to generate revenue.

Strengthening leadership is a reducible weapon. Strong leadership is not limited to understanding warning signs, but involves the ability to decide on the right measures at the right time.

Experimentation is the test of reality in turbulent conditions; there are no previous experiences to ensure that the road is right. In most cases, the implementation of new ideas cannot be done within the old structures and processes. New structures, new types of

operations, new systems and a new culture are needed. They can work in parallel with the old structures. However, only the market can give a final verdict.

The sale of the business must be done when the company is operating well. However, it's not an easy business when it goes well. The resilience of shareholders and many managers responsible for the operational area is often considerable. Yet, selling can be the best way to save a company that is in danger of losing its strategic health. It is important to note that not every potential crisis threatens the strategic health of the company, but only those crises that can affect the entire organization. When we talk about the strategic health of the company, we are talking about conditions that can destroy the business, not about crises at the level of some organizational subassemblies. This uncertainty has implications for the timing of intervention planning.

In times of austerity and uncertainty, the most important point of strategic planning remains the product, in other words, what we offer to the consumer and not the price. Of course, a high quality, low-priced product for a low-quality product will be neither profitable nor able to save the product from extinction.

Many companies today talk about cost innovations or frugal innovations. It is about the design of robust products, of the best quality, but without additives that do nothing but raise costs, without bringing a REAL Value FOR CONSUMERS. An example is the Dacia car, which recorded record sales in European markets due to the low price obtained by simple features and low-cost design: only five shades of exterior colour, different models with identical door panels, windshields built at a steep angle, to reduce production and installation costs and many other cost innovations. The simplicity of the design and the production process, the minimum equipment and a good value for money increase the resilience of the product in crises and are an important asset for a successful strategy.

An important effect of the turbulence is the change in consumer sensitivity to the elements of the marketing mix. What we know from normal times about the effect of TV commercials, promotions, or competitive pricing is no longer in line with economic uncertainty. Therefore, the company must constantly test the elasticity of the elements of the mix and revise them operatively. Another change generated by the economic crisis is the need for strategic review more often than is practiced in times of economic stability.

In the field of strategic planning, the most common error is the confusion between strategy and operational efficiency. The strategy seeks a market position and a path to the chosen position, while operational efficiency means permanent changes to achieve the best possible practice. During the crisis, managers' impression increases, according to which the current measures taken in exceptional situations they are strategic measures, although in reality, they are measures to increase operational efficiency.

Yet what is the best strategy in situations of economic instability and insecurity? Strategies based on market stability do not work. Profitable niche strategy. The company finds a valuable niche, makes a good plan and puts all its efforts in motion to reap maximum benefits. When the market is volatile, niches also become volatile. In addition, competitors may find sub-markets within the niche, leading to the niche of the company that found the niche.

The company needs to come up with a new idea that can open up a completely new market. The problem with this strategy is the enormous difficulty of finding the saving idea. Another strategic approach is to change by successive probing. The company tries to make small changes, step by step, in different directions and develops changes that work. The cost of variation also remains an issue. The partnership-based strategy is another direction that seems very promising. It revolves around the economic concept of sharing and it is illustrated by the company's spectacular results. The notion of sharing involves the combination of forces and the shared use of unique resources, in order to reduce costs and increase the

accessibility of products or services. Radical restructuring of the business, which involves total renewal, elimination of parallel directions, unprofitable or unprofitable products, refocusing the company in new directions. Huge companies have gone through such major restructuring, which obviously involves huge budgets and great difficulties in convincing shareholders. Firms can learn some of these strategic directions, and a hybrid or successive approach to different distinct strategies could ultimately be the right solution.

The success of differentiation depends on the costs allocated to differentiation. In general, the costs are quite high, and due to the crisis, many companies do not have the necessary resources. Companies that have money to invest risk reaching an unattractive price for the market. The exception is trendy technology products, such as smartphones, where demand seems to be inflexible, relatively independent of price. For regular products, the price difference between companies that have created a unique offer and cheap bidders may become too large. Customers will not be prepared to pay the excess price to buy a more expensive product and will therefore give up certain features of the product and settle for a cheaper product. In the face of economic turmoil, any process of differentiation must be based on a careful analysis of the cost-benefit ratio, as well as an analysis of customers' sensitivity to the higher cost. In difficult economic times, differentiation strategies that are based on functional benefits seem to be more effective than differentiation strategies based on intangible or emotional attributes. Strong functional attributes inspire greater consumer confidence and largely the reason for the purchase. The problem lies in the difficulty of the company to find a solid functional attribute, which has not already been confiscated by another company.

If we do not have a strong functional attribute, we must resort to an intangible attribute, provided it is valued by the market. Intangible attributes are quality, experience, expertise, innovative spirit, international character, customer orientation, care for the environment, etc. Marketing research helps us to find the attribute that is of great importance to consumers in times of crisis. In principle, a well-found intangible attribute can be even better than a tangible attribute. The company's positioning strengthens lasts longer, resists competition attacks better, and can be harder to copy by other companies.

The strategy of selling the product at the lowest price depends on the economy of scale, in other words on the company's ability to produce more and at lower costs than the rest of the market. However, in times of crisis, when consumption decreases, the volume of products sold inevitably decreases. This has three consequences: first, the possibility of obtaining a favourable cost structure disappears. Secondly, the sale of a smaller number of products cannot bring a satisfactory profit, as the products are insufficiently differentiated. Third, many firms are forced to produce private labels for large retail chains at a price that barely covers production costs. Not to mention profit, even a minimal one.

In times of crisis, price reductions when selling products with or without economies of scale become the most widespread policies to stimulate sales. This trend is based on the assumption that people have less money and want to buy cheaper products. The presumption is only partially true. Not all poor consumers want to buy cheaper. People not only buy based on the liquidity available, but also on the trust, they have in the product and the need to buy a reliable product. Consequently, firms should not reduce the price of basic brands, because the reduction does nothing but diminish the capital of the brand's reputation and destroy the company's revenue. The solution is for the company to create a more "frugal" offer under a new brand and a lower price. Good at a higher price.

The market niche strategy does not seem to be a remedy in the era of economic turmoil. First, niches are hit harder by the crisis than mass-produced goods and services. Second, in times of economic hardship, large producers expand their product portfolio to maximize total

sales, thus occupying profitable niches. As large producers have more capital, they will easily be able to displace companies that have chosen to serve a niche as their main strategy.

The strategy of imitating what other companies do can be useful in times of crisis, and the condition is that the company imitating adds value to the copied model and avoids legal disputes. Imitation should be used as a basis for innovation rather than as a method of growth.

Some types of actions can help the company to compete in times of economic turmoil:

- Reducing costs, in order to increase the competitive strength of the company;
- Monitoring consumer preferences and understanding changes in terms of preferences, product category and competition products;
- Development of strategic alliances, to strengthen the competitive position on the market;
- Development of management actions regarding customer relations and additional support for consumers, to increase loyalty and increase customer satisfaction with the company's services;
- Strengthening the image and strength of the brand, to increase the preference for our product.

Cost reduction is the most frequently and arbitrarily used solution. Firms simply select areas that have higher or less vital costs and reduce what can be reduced. A more appropriate method is the systematic analysis of all the factors that lead to expenses. In any company, costs accumulate in nine main areas:

1. Acquisitions;
2. Developments;
3. Production;
4. Logistics;
5. Distribution and services;
6. Staff;
7. Computer systems;
8. Controlling / Accounting;
9. Leadership and organization.

Numerous processes, procedures, activities, etc. can be found in each of these areas, which creates reducible costs, either because the activities are performed in excess or because they are performed uneconomically.

Marketing includes a wide inventory of levers for growth. Some levers operate smoothly in growing markets, but face problems in difficult markets or times of recession. On the other hand, levers more suitable for turbulent periods are often less commonly used during economic boom.

We are going to examine some of the potential levers available to the company.

Attracting new customers, who have similar needs to existing consumers, but are not yet users of the product. This approach works well during periods of market growth, but is less effective when the market contracts, people consume less and are more reluctant to new consumer experiences.

The influence of the users of the product to buy it more frequently or to increase the quantity consumed at a consumption occasion. In general, it is also a way of growing specific to good weather. It could also work in times of recession, provided the price is reduced, the product is explicitly positioned for regular or frequent use, and some measures are made easier.

Attracting consumers from the competition. This tactic requires great effort, primarily financial. It involves product improvement, aggressive pricing, substantial promotions and the development of distribution. In general, dislocating customers from the competition is difficult even in normal times, especially in times of crisis. A much better idea is to strengthen your customer loyalty.

Acquisition of a competitor. It can be a good move during the recession, when purchasing costs are lower. It is a sure way to increase market share. For example, the US bank Wells Fargo, which operated only in the western half of the United States, bought Wachovia Bank in 2008 and doubled its number of branches, covering the entire U.S. territory. Then, in the midst of the crisis, by 2013, to become one of the largest banks in the world, after market capitalization.

- Reducing company costs. Sometimes, during the recession, cost reduction is also used as a growth method. In general, companies reduce costs due to immediate financial constraints. The first measures aimed at reducing spending on salaries, training, advertising, marketing research and any services considered "less important" for consumers. Unfortunately, these short-term benefits weaken the company's long-term competitiveness and, ultimately, it undermines the chances of growth, but controlling the company's costs and indebtedness (if any) is a basic lever for solvency, without which we cannot talk about growth plans.
- Strengthening customer loyalty is an essential strategy, especially in times of crisis. We will discuss this topic in detail in a separate chapter. Customer loyalty stabilizes the business and, over time, leads to increased revenue. The satisfied consumers, the older they are, the more frequent they recommend to other customers the company's products.
- Identifying new markets, especially geographical (national or foreign) is a useful solution, especially in times of crisis when the home business is starting to thin out. Orientation towards new markets can be taken into account in the following situations:
 - When the target markets promise a higher yield than the home market;
 - When profits fall on the home market;
 - When our product is equipped to perfectly meet the needs of consumers in the new market;
 - When we have a "bridgehead" in the new market (a local agent, a distribution chain with extended geographical coverage, etc.).

Significant increases can also be achieved in times of crisis by innovating products and services. The telecommunications market provides a suggestive example. Usually, innovations are initially geared towards the existing market, currently served. There are several types of innovation. Thus, the company can add features to existing products (supportive innovation) or revolutionize the product as a whole, generating new benefits and behaviours (disruptive innovation). Not all companies have the capacity to produce disruptive innovations, but any company can innovate the product to make it more attractive than it was.

Business diversification is a common temptation in times of crisis, when growth and profit prospects are narrowing. However, any diversification involves entering new territory and the possible confrontation of the company with unforeseen risks. In general, diversification can be a growth option in times of crisis, only if the new business is clearly linked to the company's core business and achieves synergy effects based on complementarity. Synergy can ensure lower costs and a higher level of competitiveness.

Clark and Mills studied mergers and acquisitions (F&A) in depth and discovered seven factors that can lead to success. Analysing the factors, we can deduce three essential ideas that should be a priority for companies that are engaged in a process of merger or acquisition in times of economic uncertainty: income, synergies and economic health of the actors.

- 1) Income refers to the need to correctly estimate how much extra is earned and to approximate the increment of value that can be obtained from the merger. If the increment is small, merging should be avoided.

- 2) Synergies refer to the complementary advantages, A brings a plus that B. does not have. The synergy effects must be real (not illusory), tangible, important and achievable. If the synergies are uncertain or minor, the merger is unlikely to succeed.
- 3) Economic health presupposes that neither of the two actors of the merger is on the "slide". Mergers precipitate, instead of stopping the fall.

The merger generates a large number of improvisations determined by the unique solutions of the organizational integration process. Gathering information can be extremely demanding and dangerous. One solution is to conduct a Business Impact Analysis before the merger that determines how the main functions of the business are affected by the crisis and the merger. The analysis includes a plan to limit the risks and costs of the impact of change. This plan is very important not only for the recovery of the situation, but also especially for the continuity of the business.

Conducting a cultural audit before the merger can save companies a lot of trouble and unnecessary expense. The due diligence process (Due Diligence) should probably be extended to include careful assessment of organizational cultures.

Special attention must be paid to the management of the relationship with the staff of the two organizations. Periods of crisis automatically generate the feeling of uncertainty, insecurity and demoralization. In the context of the crisis, people are expecting staff reductions, job cuts, downward revisions to pay contracts, assistance with ongoing projects, changing criteria for assessing personal skills and other worrying changes. Three measures are indicated in this context: monitoring continuous stress of employees; transparent and permanent communication with employees; strong involvement of employees in the process of inter-organizational merger (employee buy-in).

- When the market for the company's core business is contracted, diversification of the business object can be a solution to maintain resilience. The core business is no longer able to absorb shocks, fluctuations and market declines, even if the company continues to allocate resources to its core business. However, the tendency for excessive diversification in several directions of activity could be risky. It does nothing but disperse resources when the company needs them most, and multiple diversification is no guarantee that the selected directions are correct. It seems that the best solution is a moderate diversification.

- Another condition for the success of diversification in crisis conditions is the possibility for the company to obtain cost reductions. There are several ways:

- Increasing the volume, by increasing the utilization rate of the production capacity;
- Increasing productivity;

- Use of so-called divisible assets. In other words, companies that have cellular resources can be used together for the core business and for the new direction of business. Examples of such resources are information technology, a strong brand name, distribution channels, global customers, foreign relations. Shared resources reduce the company's costs.

- The brand name is always an important factor for the success of a diversification, even when the payment seems to be completely blocked. A recent example is the diversification of Zara, in the field of their home furniture: towels, bed linen, tablecloths, bathrobes, kitchen towels, etc. Many analysts have looked with scepticism at the entry of a clothing company into a home laundry market, extremely defragmented with a huge number of suppliers. Online retailers, department stores, supermarkets, hypermarkets, specialty stores and more, all sell these products in abundance. Yet, Zara has dared and seems to be successful. The explanation is the brand, already very strong on the market. With a high share of brand recognition, the company has a great chance on a fragmented market, precisely because of fragmentation. It can quickly build a segment of buyers, with minimal costs for

ads and promotions. In addition, a famous brand is always advantaged in a category of products where needs can be created that do not exist in reality, for example: you have a white towel, you have a red one. "

- The diversification of Pepsi, by incorporating the manufacturer Frito-Lay, does not seem to be a success. The case offers some interesting lessons, highlighted in The Economist magazine. The choice to diversify or, conversely, to focus on a single main area depends on the characteristics of the market. Focusing on a single field is successful in large and developed markets, where each product category can reach a high level of complexity (for example, tens or hundreds of variants of a product), and the number of retailers is relatively small. Instead, diversification is preferable for less developed but fragmented markets. In such markets, it is good for the company to have multiple product categories and a large sales force.

- Finally, if the market response to the diversification of companies is anaemic, the best thing is for the company to pay new attention to the main object of activity. At the beginning of the crisis, Rolls Royce forecast a decrease in air traffic and demand for aircraft engines. Consequently, it decided to diversify its activity, manufacturing other equipment for terrestrial and marine activities, among others for oil companies. In the meantime, the price of oil has fallen. Air traffic has not declined, but oil companies' investment in Rolls Royce-type equipment has declined. Probably for other reasons, the diversification of Rolls Royce has generated questionable results, and the company is currently examining the return to its core business, the construction of aircraft engines and, possibly, the separation of other areas from the core business.

3. Many companies consider that price reductions are inevitable in the face of economic turmoil, because the company needs additional short-term sales or has to do fat to the reductions operated by the competition. However, the danger of the Army entering a vicious circle of successive destructive reductions is very real. Price reduction probably should not be the first choice of management. The company can be better protected by differentiating from the competition than by lowering the price.

The most useful differentiation can be obtained by stronger customer orientation and adding additional value to the product, services, customer relationship or company image.

Ultimately, the purpose of the reduction is to increase the quantities sold. Theoretically, increasing volumes could reduce costs due to the experience curve. In times of turmoil and market volatility, however, sales may not increase enough to provide expected revenues and cover baskets. Consequently, profitability decreases, instead of increasing. Insufficient sales to offset the price decline are not the only potentially destructive effect. The lower price eliminates customers who would pay more. It is important for the company to remember that price is not the only factor that determines demand.

In difficult times, price reductions must be made at the same time as cost reductions, Wal-Mart and IKEA, for example, have reduced costs by carefully examining the value proposition and eliminating unimportant attributes and benefits for consumers. As a result, over the last few years, companies have managed to increase their market share and maintain profitability.

Eventually, the company could launch a price reduction action, if it knows that it has the lowest variable costs on the market, and the other companies will not be able to keep their hair with a substantial reduction. However, it is difficult to assume that the company can have reliable information about the variable costs of the competition.

In general, the reactions of companies to a competitor who has reduced the price are not very prompt or lacking. Many companies are characterized by a certain organizational inertia, have predetermined plans and priorities that cannot be set aside immediately, do not notice the severity of the price change or a constant with enough delay. However, even if the

company could react faster, the chances of counteracting are quite limited. The worst option is to reduce the price, possibly by a fraction below the price of the competition. On the other hand, the company could be more successful if it introduced a new product at a lower price, which would compete with the price reduction in the competition.

If a competitor reduces the price, the company must verify to what extent the new price is associated with a competitive advantage the level of the product or services. When the new price is accompanied by other competitive advantages, it is good that the company does not try to answer, even if it will lose market share - if the direct competitor has a product identical to the one of the company that sells cheaper, it is likely reasonable for the firm to lower the price. Nevertheless, the products are rarely one hundred percent identical.

The need to measure the overall performance of the company increases the difficult times in economic terms. Companies need continuous feedback for achievements and failures, instead of annual reviews.

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